

The Research-Innovation-Entrepreneurship Deliverable from the Perspective of the Vision-Mission Statements among Zimbabwe's Higher Education Institutions

By

Dr Vincent Mnkandla

Abstract

From the empirical evidence, at the heart of the visions of excellence, technopreneurship, world class, knowledge hub, advancement of humanity, premier, etc. is the drive to propel a dynamic research-innovation-entrepreneurship (RIE) deliverable befitting the aspirations and demands of the sustainable development superstructure. In other words, what the statements attest to is a high profile potential learning product with outstanding competencies, skills and abilities, in particular creativity, innovativeness, knowledge generation and sharing, professionalism, integrity, equity, patriotism, diversity and much more. The envisaged outcome is a manpower windfall of thinkers, builders, improvers and providers rock solid in demonstrable RIE skills, hence, capable to advance the prospective, interactive continuity between the scientific-technological and the productive-business worlds for more and better rates of return. The RIE deliverable, therefore, is the proverbial Siamese triplets that achieve more together while challenged individually. In advancing it as the top aspiration, the institutions fully recognise its role as the springboard to distil and harness market opportunities, networks and all. The only disturbing gap is the extent it consistently eludes the local markets, perpetually courting the false infinite or lopsided, short-lived growth accelerations, marginalised development, and conspicuous consumptions.

Some keywords: *vision-mission statements; superintelligent; copy-write; technological infinite; potential learning product; technocapitalism; fait accompli*

Introduction

This Paper is distilled from a study of the vision-mission-values statements of four science and technology universities in Zimbabwe. Basically, it discusses the theoretical and practical fortunes of the research-innovation-entrepreneurship (RIE) mandate from the perspective of the statements. The empirical evidence reveals how pronouncing the statements is one thing, while successfully living them is quite another. The immense potential for a well marshalled RIE deliverable is countered by a plethora of faults and breaks that complicate the institutional wherewithal to propel the national dispensation. Paradoxically, the institutions find themselves in an unenviable *bone voyage* with great prospects, but wormed by freak controversies associated with disvalue education. It is hoped the paper will spark interest for further study and research on this vital aspect of the mandates to enlarge capacity for lasting solutions.

The vision-mission perspective

The enactment of the vision-mission statements is to inspire the academy through foresighted and farsighted constructions to attain the gold standard. An import from business, the drive is to emulate and duplicate the market model in non-market establishments to achieve a higher and better potential learning product. The latter defines the designer intelligence achievable in the

context of product massification-cum-quality assurance to match growing supply and demand. In other words, it is the gross output of superintelligent products well-equipped with requisite strength, motivation and fit to foster the technological society for sustainable development. Mobilised by the dense vision-values lexicons that include excellence, world class, knowledge hub, technopreneurship, commercialisation, advancement of humanity, premier, pioneering, etc. the target is to acclimatise the dream efforts for clinically productive and morally efficient products befitting the sustainable development goal.

Central to the emancipatory eugenics is the drive to morph a technologically level playing field and, therefore, befitting equality and equity in the ground rules moulding human civilization (Bostrom, 2012). The eugenics of *Techno sapiens*, or *Homo technicus*, or *Homo technologicus* – they-who-use-technology, especially design technology – characterises the graded capitalism with strong roots in vibrant technology arts, in the power of corporations, and in new networks and forms of organizational behaviour. Hence, singularity, techno-progressivism, the technology exponential syndrome, the technological infinite, or technocapitalism and other such paradigms now configure the role of technology as the oxygen firing the RIE deliverable to suite the uniquely complex, complicated and sophisticated environments of today (Suarez-Villa, 2009, 2014). Accordingly, the ensuing designer product is by description: innumerable in number; immense in diversity; illimitable in knowledge, skills and values; inexhaustible in ideas, inventions and innovations; robotic in efficiency; prodigious in productivity/entrepreneurship; limitless in consumption; democratic in governance; and is transitionally renewable, *ad infinitum*.

These are superintelligent humans adept at exploiting the intangibles of creativity, work capacity, intrinsic motivation, network designs, technological infrastructures and converting them into more and better instrumentally useful, culturally-transmissible innovations (Bostrom, 2012; Suarez-Villa, 2014) high in exergy-consumability values. This is maximum useful work output/goods and services extractable from systems as they reversibly move into equilibrium. It is only an emancipated workforce able to galvanise the envisioned technocapitalist trending where research, innovation and entrepreneurship are both the core tools and envisioned outcomes.

In achieving the technological infinites: infinite production, infinite development, infinite growth, and infinite consumption the system simultaneously cuts back on the vagaries of the false dawn, or proxy capitalism, or the technology regression syndrome – the antitheses of the unlimited, linear progression from ignorance and poverty to knowledge and modern life, the steady inexorable change to more and better social wellbeing, which is what sustainable development is all about. So, the RIE deliverable is the instrument to mobilise the *Homo technicus-Homo simplex* divide and uplift the disadvantaged segments of society that fail or are excluded from the social benefits enjoyed by *Homo technicus*, yet their survival requires the know-how and culture of *Homo technicus*. *Homo simplex* is a living reality across the African landscape given the volumes of *illionnaires* and *nillionnaires*: being reference to the sick and poverty stricken African masses (Pipim, 2013) stemming from the inability to access the science and technology resources. Ultimately, the targeted potential learning product is one whose ideas

and artisanship skills translate into proficient psycho-technics with high-value practical throughput.

There are two critical elements behind the technology trending. First, is the intelligence deployed between unqualified versus qualified intelligence. The former is the rational, scientific, innovative and consummate (decision making and problem solving) competency, based on scholarly intellection, quality emotional intelligence, crowned with the capacity to analyse, organize, strategize, and produce goods and services for the betterment of society. In contrast, the latter is characteristically superficial, fragile, flawed and lacks transparency and depth to require persistent defence against incessant complaints and attacks. It equates with the norms of rational ignorance, or mental economy, or suboptimal cognition, extending to conscious incompetence, unconscious competence and other intelligence dysfunctions.

The other is curricula leverage in general, and science and technology education in particular, embracing STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) and GRIN (genetics, robotics, information technology and nanotechnology) technologies education to accentuate full access to the array of technological attributes and, therefore, full equalization for survival in the advanced environmental environments (McCarthy, 2012). Epistemologically, the learned scientific and technological arts must convert into a spontaneous psyche, into internalized custom and practice, and into a generic standard that resonates within the people themselves as they experience the turbulent challenges around them. Hence, thus far, the limited capacity to innovate, in particular to harness and transform the technology exponential syndrome into concrete products and services, places a great premium on a high value RIE deliverable concomitant with the demand for usual and novel applications befitting modernity.

Operationally, the vision-mission statements of some of the institutional units reflect the above aspirations. For example, the vision of the Research and Postgraduate Centre of the Bindura University of Science Education (BUSE, 2013) is “to be the core provider of resources that support the teaching, learning, research and community service activities undertaken at BUSE.” Equally, the mission is “to provide current, relevant and expert support to research as a major activity as well as provide information on postgraduate issues in accordance with the International University Standards in fulfilment of its role to facilitate teaching, learning, research and community service at BUSE.” Lastly, ‘competence, teamwork and professionalism’ make up the core values. The National University of Science and Technology (NUST) Research and Innovation Office crowns the epistemology, declaring its vision “to be a reputable centre of excellence in research and innovation for sustainable development.” Implied and set to be unravelled is the uncompromising optimization imperative embedded in the technocapitalist drive marking the point of departure from and entry into a new dawn different from what has gone before.

This is the nature of the language prefacing the RIE epistemology. It is quite a mouthful and, apparently, its unfamiliarity can only mean that one is operating at the periphery of the melting pot. A deep immersion would be quite apposite, which this paper can only partially proffer.

Institutionalization of the RIE deliverable

The basis of institutional existence is to purify the products at source – i.e., beneficiate the economy, the people, society and the environment at large. For that reason the RIE deliverable is the heart of the mandates, accounting for knowledge generation, new discoveries and novel ideas, and artisanal frameworks, improvements and inventions to meet multi-purpose goals and targets. The Harare Institute of Technology (HIT) exalts that role, declaring itself “the stimulant of scholarship in innovation through cultivating commitment towards technopreneurial leadership and commercialising technology through professionalism rooted in integrity.” Similarly, at the 2013 graduation ceremony, the NUST Vice-Chancellor remarked that ‘...research, innovation and entrepreneurship are the key to Zimbabwe’s recovery and you are at the forefront of that as young people’, precisely how the deliverable is *the* noblest diplomatic passport to the world class status, industrialization, competitiveness, reputation, pioneering and other such visions.

Guided by the Research Council of Zimbabwe policy goals and the related National Research Priorities, the research magnifies deployment of scientific methods to innovate and entrepreneur. Accordingly, the target is to strengthen capacity development in science, technology and innovation (STI); to learn and utilise emergent technologies to accelerate development; to accelerate commercialization of research results; to search for scientific solutions to global environmental challenges; to mobilise resources and popularise science and technology; and to foster international collaboration in STI (Lemarchand and Schneegans, 2014, p.101). That being the case, continuously churned out are priority themes covering national capacity: on social sciences and humanities; on sustainable environmental and resource management (climate, energy, water, land, etc.); on promoting and maintaining good health; and on safeguarding the national security of Zimbabwe in line with the global sustainability information framework (GSIF). Noticeably missing are the engineering trades and related producers of capital goods and services – the backbone of technocapitalism.

The researcher’s incisive mind to create or innovate is the essence of the epistemology. It is the capacity to simultaneously crack, stimulate, manipulate and convert matter, energy or data and information, under correct conditions and combinations, into tangible market products, goods and services, or into entrepreneurial ideas and, therefore, successful enterprise or business opportunity. The perpetual betterising is either stimulated through incremental innovation or through disruptive innovation, or both. In short, either the sustaining or radical change model is the basis for ideal generation of products or services, failing which, in place of constructive innovation, is real de-innovation – the ruinous, rigidification of the status quo.

Meanwhile, given the deepening decline in formal sector enterprises, entrepreneurship defined in terms of the 4Es – entrepreneurship, employability, equal opportunity and employment creation, coupled with the much more radical lot of empowerment, indigenisation and affirmative action, is the prime slogan and drive. In line with the Black Economic Empowerment laws (BEE), it not only means reversing colonial practices, but also to provide the miracle cures to economic

growth and employment equity through local ownership of the means of production, skills development and other socioeconomic measures.

The technopreneurial argument is basically that, alone, technology is incapable to generate the much desired entrepreneurship and, therefore, employment. Equally, alone entrepreneurship is insufficient for the much needed capital goods and hi-tech businesses and projects of the 21st Century with the capacity to grow the economy and ensure sufficient employment. In line with Lou's (2013) category of skills, demand is for: *Thinkers* who are “the visionaries, strategists, intellects, and creators of the world” from whom spring or originate all big ideas be it new products, new services, and different ways of fulfilling the mandates; *Builders* who are the experts and professionals “who take an idea from scratch and convert it into something tangible”; *Improvers* who “upgrade, change or make a repeatable process better”, and *Providers* who “...execute or maintain a repeatable process” at the level befitting excellence. While the relationship is usually marked by a few *Thinkers* at one end of the scale versus the bulky range of *Providers* at the other end, what is important is a balanced job-mix with all categories represented and operating beyond ‘routine maintenance functions’ – typical of the curriculum at this moment in time (Nyathi, 2014).

In the final analysis, the potential learning product must ingrain the technological culture and show greater pitch and trending to make/create/innovate than merely to know; to build more than to consume; to capitalise more than to maintain; and to be entrepreneurs more than to sell its labour. This is genuine configuration of the RIE calculus capable to reduce the most abundant materials like soil-rock matter and animal-plant cellulose and fibre into numerous products mainly foodstuffs and different material ware; to harness renewable energy resources; to convert fluids like air and water into potable resources, chemicals, fuels and oils to sustain national demand, and to safeguard the environment. This calls for a dexterous materials technology culture rich in design research, service design, market research, etc. to leverage the supply-demand relationships to ultimately ensure real equity in the provision of products, goods and services, free of downgrade factors and processes. The sustained practical professionalism reflects product role as forceful change agents, strong in knowledge fusion or materials and product development, information and communication technologies, service brands, and market intelligence (BUSE, 2013).

A synthesis of the empirical findings

Drawing data and information from online and document sources, interviews and the diversity survey, the fieldwork produced a lexically diverse cargo from which was synthesised the RIE theme/deliverable. Briefly, the corroborative data summed the deliverable as focused on: establishing research and innovation offices, centres or faculty units, science parks and entrepreneurship schemes; building a knowledge-based society; achieving knowledge-based solutions; more development-oriented research and innovation; enterprise development; technology diplomacy; intellectual property rights; skilled citizens; and greater concentration on entrepreneurship, to cite the evidence.

The diversity survey produced a normal/adequate (N/A) rating, at an average mean of 2.5 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.82 as the final outcome for the 11 predefined indicator variables

that were measured (see Figure 1). The data specified a weak/bland RIE deliverable. This was despite the relatively high functional/commendable (F/C) frequency ratings across the bulk of the indicators, to mean that there was potential for an above N/A deliverable. According to the graph, there is commendable promise with the constituency servicing mandate, the graduate competency levels, institutional competitiveness and science and technology outcomes all of which enjoy fairly high F/C ratings, indeed, with a stronger pull towards exceptional/world class (E/W) and much less towards NA and inadequate/substandard (I/S) ratings.

Meanwhile, the much coveted E/W and, therefore, the most valid measure indicating a vibrant RIE culture, precisely what the institutions want, deserve and work by, is extremely weak, only marginally visible in the few indicators of constituency servicing, graduate competency levels, leadership status and institutional competitiveness where it records an average mean rating of 3.0. Somehow, the institutional ideals are more at odds with the reality on the ground.

The combined IS-NA ratings peak at the transfers of technological innovations and inventions (82%), followed by employment creation (69%), conditions for continuous improvement (63%) and, lastly, entrepreneurship training (55%) – practical professionalism where it matters the most. From the high SD values the divergent perceptions give the deliverable the benefit of the doubt: either acknowledging or dismissing it outright, revealing how events are not correspondent across the board. Significant gaps render the RIE deliverable far from the excellence capable to build the El Dorado that is Zimbabwe: an indictment of the theoretical capacity to meet constituency needs.

Figure 1. The Research-Innovation-Entrepreneurship deliverable

But, just as eloquent are the myriad trials and tribulations which both explain and complicate the above verdicts. Challenges of out-dated/obsolete equipment; small IT bandwidths; limited new machine supplies; inadequate physical infrastructures; curricula duplications; excessive lip service, hence, limited actual deliverables (publications, patents, etc.) universities are judged by; too much teaching and coaching, not how to make a computer, but only how to use it, or highly empirical programmes with very little practical work; provision of basic knowledge at the expense of applications, especially technological information which will make the products unique; need for lecturers who are less theory minded, but who, while theoretically equipped, are more hands-on oriented; dependence on textbooks than learning-by-doing or practical science from labs; lack of innovative leadership which is always apologetic about its inefficiencies; staff only eager to earn money rather than fulfil the vision-mission, continue to electrocute the delivery.

In summary, everything points towards a stalled RIE deliverable – potentially strong but heavily countered by immense weaknesses surrounding productive curricular transformations. While both new and traditional infrastructures are in place to support the aspiration to raise more and better skilled personnel, as well as keep the research-innovation capabilities of society measuring to world standards, the drawbacks are as forceful as they are elusive and formidable. Teaching and learning are going on but amidst colossal faults and breaks generating fragile results and outcomes.

Discussion

The RIE deliverable is everything that the institutions want to be: it is the heart of the world class potential learning product and all that it stands for. To sustain the torque pressure, both physical and academic infrastructures operate at full capacity in collaboration with local and world renowned organizations like the Computer Society of Zimbabwe, technical and vocational education and training institutions, the Scientific and Industrial Research and Development Centre and its affiliate Institutes, the Confederation of Zimbabwe industries, world universities and technology institutes, including the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and its affiliates – the African Regional Intellectual Property Organization (ARIPO), the Zimbabwe Intellectual Property Office, and institutional technology and innovation support centres.

The excellence and, therefore, productivity and impact of the delivered RIE is measured in volumes of inventions and research presentations and citations in various forums, more so in refereed and open source journals like *Science and Nature*, *Scopus* and the *Zimbabwe Journal of Science and Technology*. Critical issues include science and technology pedagogy, production and manufacturing, research and development, and commercialization, on one hand, and maximization of entrepreneurship through development, incubation and transfer of ideas, results and products, on the other. The ultimate objective, as the HIT (2015, p.4) observes, is to “create a culture where students and staff are both scholars and technopreneurs”, hence, “give the nation meaning and ability to build futures which for now cannot be imagined” (HIT, 2011, pp.2–3).

Hence, through the Medici Effect the research exploits cross-cultural diversity to generate

practicable solutions from the diverse experiences, ideas and entities; through cyneetics, it brings experts from various backgrounds together to generate technical solutions; through abductive reasoning, it pools lay ideas and concepts and vets them for their commercial value; through design research and digital technology, it engineers and rebrands models of new and old products, goods and services; and through predictive analytics (Big Data), it fathoms the actionable intelligence embedded within the vast troves of data that businesses and governments generate which, when subjected to analysis, can offer useful forecasts at an acceptable level of reliability and efficiency for application by different units in the *econogram*. With the transformative agenda geared towards renewed investment in ideas and people (BUSE, 2013), the target is enhanced product proficiency to translate scientific exploits into commercializable innovations, entrepreneurships and other creative artefacts in such a way that, in the words of the NUST they can stand their own in the industrial, commercial and informal sector markets – genuine RIE juggernauts.

A wide variety of utility products continue to grace the market. They include solar dryers for farm produce, egg and fruit incubators, moringa products, tobacco grading technology, vermiculture technology for waste management, activated carbon granules for gold extraction, sanitary pads, solar power plants, the biochar stove, solar-powered railroad robot technology, synthesis of silica gels, a farm humidity-pH sensor, an expandable bending machine for the construction industry, the optical coherence tomography surface imaging system and agricultural equipment to name a few, extending to information technology and myriad incubation platforms, accelerators, kick-starters, new prototypes, tech-hubs, applications and inventions for patenting. The massive outpouring of ideas sustains. Through expanding human needs, the RIE throughput constitutes the solid base for inventions and new solutions guaranteeing the exciting technological breakthroughs that enhance institutional integrity.

In comparison to the incredible global leap forward, the above innovations amount to appropriate technologies. Measured against the Ford assembly plant, industrial farming, brain stimulating devices, the Drinkable Book (for water purification) and DNA testing and other specialisms, they are no more than mere replications, still to stimulate the Technopark's investment drive. The 2015 Research and Intellectual Outputs: Science, Engineering and Technology Expo (RIO-SET) revealed the magnitude of the adoptive and adaptive technologies and innovations on display. It can be argued, though that, this is a normal development in science and technology, since there is really nothing new, but diversity in discoveries and improvements on what already exists. What is needed is full mastery of the psycho-technics entailed in the bio-physical properties of the materials or in engineering, information, marketing and environmental technology. In the words of Gardner (2011) and Lee (2012), Reboot, the significance of the 'generated utility value is developing better ways for people to access the services they need from the most mundane (like commuting to work) to the most life-altering (like accessing quality healthcare)' in the most economical and efficient ways practicable.

That makes the above products significantly secondary rather than primary inventions/innovations which reveals the nascent tendency to substitute, modify, recreate, remodel, readjust and repackage in place of clear-cut breakthroughs into uncharted high

capacity tech domains. Their field frequency to meet the jobs-to-do criteria resembles a meteorite in the dark sky, the challenges of venture capital notwithstanding. The Gartner hype-cycle 'peak-trough of disillusionment' see-saw is typically characteristic. This reproduces the traditional foreign technology domination to the most basic levels, sustaining the dictum of developing countries producing what they do not consume and consuming what they do not produce. In the process, the dilemma of the Malthusian empty belly or eating machine, of poverty in the midst of vast wealth, persists.

Without doubt, therefore, the RIE limitations are responsible for the colossal constituency drawbacks, creating societies that are more consumptive than productive; that are more dependent than creative; and that remain perplexed by the inner spirit of science and technology in this day and age. In response, the contagious vision-values statements of intellectual freedom, commitment, teamwork, strategic partnerships, dynamism, technical skills and professionalism echo quite succinctly efforts to galvanise the RIE deliverable to foster the stemitized culture of creative thinking, tech-design and programing, analytic problem solving and much more. Technically, the target is deep integration, involving intensive skills mixtures across the board in order to harness opportunities while stemming the gross challenges.

Historically, despite the 1% national investment, institutional research has contributed immensely to propel vibrant socio-economic activity. Although, factually, the results of most of the researches are already known, it has not dampened morale, with a commendable annual output of about 200 published papers, averaging 0.6% of the total institutional expenditures. But, as a result of insufficient funding, most of the research goes uncommercialized or is transferred elsewhere only to come back as (expensive) end products or services. As the HIT puts it, developments rest on the 'seeding' in terms of capacity building with success realisable when patents (or IPs) begin to roll out. Also, the introduction of 'Open Access' in the institutional library repositories has enhanced public science communication and, therefore, the visibility and affordability of the researches.

RIE glitches and challenges

Figure 1 discounts the version that the vision-mission statements have the critical wherewithal to achieve the much needed RIE deliverable. The IS-N/A ratings across the bulk of the indicators, as a consequence of the multiple challenges cited above, provide enough evidence on the dilemma of the market model over which the institutions have very little influence, let alone capacity to unravel. What is clear is that it is hard for the RIE deliverable to firm strong roots in sync with the Rostow model, more so outside the stage of mass consumption. Powerful forces induce open and latent diminishing returns, hence, subjecting the deliverable to considerable inertia. The dearth in commercialisation skills translates into pragmatically low-tech scientists, at best mere improvers and providers than critical thinkers and builders. The much wounded science and technology curriculum emerges as the evidence of the massive ebb: dynamically and generatively inept and inert and atypically creative, inventive and of limited worth to the local scapes.

Behind the quagmire lies a host of factors at play that begin with the curriculum itself which, epistemologically, is international in focus and is conscientiously kept in tandem with changes in the global arena – confirming the dilemma of the ‘Western university in Africa’ (Mabhena, 2016a). While making it easy to benchmark with global institutions, the challenge is the level of freedom from or subservience to the more powerful institutions, worse the ideo-philosophies of the likes of Fordism, McDonaldization and other transnational corporations, resulting in limited control and mere followership of global curricula trends, a condition that blunts and distorts the RIE deliverable. In a nutshell, the dilemma of content and context simply traps the deliverable in the anachronisms of adoption and adaptation of foreign technologies at the expense of local design and service. Hence, to fit the test mark, the research must pass the international test first before accreditation locally, which translates into American or Chinese technology being the most suited to the Zimbabwean institutions and scarcely for, about, and by themselves.

As much at stake is the blurred distinction between necessary and unnecessary research, more so, whether or not the market can sustain luxuries. Unable to weather the trough of disillusionment, following the peak of expectations and, therefore, complication, high cost and other forms of market relevance, the researches soon turn into idle capacity. It is no exaggeration that the immense pressure for quick, rapid publications is churning out superficial writings, critiques, articles and dossiers, reflecting vested interests, secrecy and topic-based biases and prejudices. To Lewis (2007, p.9), the pressure renders “academic writing duller, less adventurous, and more technical, since junior faculty members opt to write what they know to be acceptable to the journals and academic presses”, linearly, “leading to the production of much more nonsense.” Consequently, the prestigiously redundant researches soon contribute to the market glut of academic litter from the rising volumes of inflated parallel publications, not necessarily plagiarised copy-writes, with practically very little to show for it.

As a result, the research studies are potentially reduced to the usual copy-write fame rather than deep, clinical searches for innovative models compatible with the evolving realities. Mabhena (2016a, para.8) puts it eloquently arguing that “Intellectually we are really not exerting ourselves enough; we keep allowing quality and rigour to remain a preserve of whites and Europeans”, hence, justifying the maxim that ‘blacks are lazy’ or are of low intelligence. Scholarship is more fastidious about conventional cosmetics rather than socially functional and productive researches that can withstand the pressures of public scrutiny, as well as unlock the gridlocked technometrics. Arguing further, Mabhena (para.9) describes as naive the expectation of more and better results when “researchers in our universities know by now that the theories and methodologies that still guide our researches are still the rusty colonial relics that lead us back to the findings and conclusions of intellectual imperial masters.” The irony is how the cloning still fails to commercialise even some of the most basic IPs and discoveries that have always been known and applied in other contexts. Concern to intensify the research lacks corresponding concern to intensify commercial entrepreneurialism so that policy works on the ground.

Taking the debate further, if the products, goods and services were directly proportional to the amount of research undertaken, the massive ideological tie to, and material dependency on, foreign technological outcomes would now be a thing of the past. Instead, much of the evidence

points towards the research as purely for purposes of academic qualifications, staff promotions, pedagogy, institutional visibility and graduate certifications rather than a tool for broader socio-economic progress. Not only are the researches averse to philosophical experiences they are unaccustomed to, challenges of reflexivity, textuality and decontextualization, coupled with intense concern with technical adjudications point to the bulk of them as more largely for appearances and immediate gratification and not much beyond. Largely opaque, prescriptive and progressively more pedantic, they are guilty of naïve realism and failure to demonstrate their practical role as tools to work the environment and promote social wellbeing through the frames and understandings of the ambient populations.

Hence, varying with the fortunes the researches encounter, once the objective has been attained, nothing much of substance takes place any more. Instead, threats of enclaving, resocialization or termination always loom large. In enclaving the innovation is isolated and restricted usually to where it started; in resocialization, hostility and pressure force the innovators to fall back in line with prevailing traditional values and practices; and, in termination, as a result of lack of sustained interest or outright opposition, the innovation is eliminated altogether. And effecting a revival can be quite a nightmare.

Therefore, besides the keen interest on the RIE deliverable, there are limited formations and metrics to stimulate a cross-wide innovation culture – that is, how staff and students are nurtured to think, act and symbolise innovation, in much the same way they communicate with one another innovatively, perpetuating conflict between the populist politics and proletariat versus the intellectual elite with its quasi-concordant research. In fact, the weak public science communication isolates the researches from their hinterland leading to the bulk of them disappearing into thin air. Meanwhile, consumerism induces mass desertions among the skilled, condemning the country to global marginalization and dependency. Equally, the habit factor strengthens the spectre of economic workplaces and, as such, stakeholders are least eager to ruffle the status quo and stand the institutions on their heads all for the sake of research and innovation.

Two issues emerge alongside this challenge. First, the absence of a powerful science fiction tradition, coupled with the dense network of neoliberal specifications enshrined in the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the WIPO's IP policy systems stifle and close rather than facilitate RIE space. A rignarole of landmines, mostly rules, restrictions and stipulations (patents, trademarks, industrial designs and copyright) which amount to sophisticated mechanisms of disguised protectionism at the gateways of the industrial markets, stuff the cooperation route. Briefs like the 'rules of origin' policy simply continue to promote the technological exports of the North at the expense of the South. Meanwhile, the inherent disadvantages with the IP system, like the dearth of local examiners, pose big problems to access patents as well as enforce copyright locally. In the final analysis, the IP system amounts to technological imperialism the institutions can scarcely generate maximum benefit out of to realise the 'mythical catch up' to the industrial North or East. As if a permanent arrangement, the institutions are ready to receive once the North has decided or produced for all to consume. What

bears fruit is complicity and compliance as the nature of the game, flirting with dim hopes and false victories.

Second, is slavery to the logic of economic competition against the powerful roadblocks and headwinds the institutions face. With education now a commodity one buys rather than a vocation one enters, it is all a question of money speaks. As a result of weak and erratic funding, coupled with the country's poor global rating (above 120) and multilateral and bilateral support that is in limbo, the RIE deliverable is a seed that has fallen on hard ground. With the institutions running on quarter-empty and, yet, fancied to fulfil the 'Prime' estate, it is difficult for it to flourish. Erratic enrolments, strained service delivery and incessant staff-student body industrial actions, as the products are reduced to informal employment, the punctured RIE barometer is not only unable to sense the requisite pressure and growth changes, it is incapable to successfully usher the desired competitiveness. Equally, the acidic policies render entrepreneurship a macro bureaucracy tool "...feeding people illusions of unending economic growth and fairy tales of how they too can get rich" to secure social stability to attract foreign direct investment (Ngwenya, 2016, p.B2).

Arguably, the rising levels of unemployment even among higher education graduates remain the major cause for concern, suggesting serious policy exaggeration. Critically, the blending mismatch between broad learning and skills training means the products exit the institutions ill-equipped for optimal labour market roles. Lack of start-up resources aside, many regard entrepreneurship as disguised unemployment, only suitable for the informal sector, hence, opting to be employed rather than to start their own businesses. Recounting his experience, an undergraduate at a NUST seminar in 2014 argued that it was much better to go through formal employment first before starting an own business venture. If anything, then, the new entrepreneurs descend to the informal sector out of necessity from which they skip out as soon as better opportunities present themselves elsewhere. In other words, they would rather have a stable job than be self-employed which they regard a menial practice (Philipp, 2010). Also, it is common cause that, while necessary, because of their nature and the huge capital outlays entailed, some disciplines like the atmospheric sciences, aeronautics engineering, medical nursing, astrophysics and science and technology education do not readily lend themselves to entrepreneurship, worse in a decimated economy.

This is against the argument whether universities are the best vehicle to impart the requisite hard skills previously offered through apprenticeship and in-house training methodologies by sector-specific Associations, Institutes and Societies. The schemes did a better job in terms of sunken skills with greater entrepreneurial potential, plus the products did not easily and readily succumb to vices like inefficiency and corruption. While the school-based education compensates the 5–8 years education and training with one year internship, the product has never been the same. Hence, many are persuaded to concur with the argument for students to 'stop out' of university, since, chances are they are more likely to achieve entrepreneurial breakthroughs on their own than with more formal education (The Thiel Institute, 2011; Grasgreen, 2013).

Writing in the Telegraph, Wright (2013, para.8) argues that entrepreneurship is a ‘nature than a nurture’ cause. As she puts it, true to fact, the operations and mechanics of business management can be learned. The challenge is converting the learned idea or ideas into ‘a well-run, sustainable operation’ – a feat not everyone is capable of undertaking. In her view ‘instincts’ come into the equation as the “key skills of sparking somebody’s imagination of creativity, boldness and the desire to take risks.” This is why “some people will be more suited to entrepreneurship than others”, which boils down to the fact that there are ‘exceptional’ people and not everyone is ‘exceptional’ for business (Robertson, 2015).

On that score the entrepreneurship lobby overlooks the fundamentals of the perception–reality gradient and, therefore, managing a business successfully: *inter alia*, the capitalist spirit and the related traits of risk awareness, attitudes, discipline, attention, business climate, financial support, capability, safety, experience, and handling failure. Apart from the fact that the skills take time to ingrain, master, transfer and deliver, with beginners the least qualified to handle them, many people just do not have the ‘instincts’ for entrepreneurship. It is begging too much to expect the classroom to transform all into entrepreneurs, more so given the python-effect of transnational monopolies, oligopolies and duopolies. The open market is as stifled and disabled as it is captured and controlled to promote unbridled hegemony.

As Grasgreen observes (2013, para.3), a point echoed by Wright (2013), “the traditional model needs to be totally rethought and resurrected as something different.” In other words, what needs to be interrogated the most is not whether entrepreneurship is ‘nature or nurture’, but our capacity to critique the concept beyond the level of a *fait accompli* which it has become, incidentally now equating to skills, further confusing the education outcomes (Akinola, 2015). As things stand, even graduates well-schooled in business management find the entrepreneurship practice hard, tough and even not worth the effort (Wright, 2013). Among some of the reasons, Schramm of UP Global (2013) argues that the programmes are business-centred rather than entrepreneurship oriented, with the latter just one of many courses in business management. Further, the bulk of the teachers lack the entrepreneurship qualification, often with the generated ideas half-baked or too simplistic to roll out a business, while the usual right–wrong grading approach means that the students are in it for the wrong reasons of good grades rather than genuine entrepreneuring based on creativity and effort. To add salt to the injury, special prizes are awarded for distinction passes and rarely for other initiatives. Lastly, is the lack of incentives to launch the plans upon completion, to which Philipp (2010) would add the culture of the extended family as part of the dark cloud engulfing entrepreneurship. By making employment a serious obligation to the clan, the pressure hampers job creation causing many to retreat from starting businesses in fear of the burden.

Last but not least are the contradictions among the entrepreneurship measures that reproduce unemployment and its ilk quite profusely. Automated world class manufacturing interventions, robotics and the Indigenisation policy are classic examples. But, more lethal has been the dynamics of the latter which, despite its noble cause, has continued to decimate the economic carcass, fuelling capital flight and keeping investors at bay (Bloc, 2014; Mangundhla, 2014). To Robertson (2015), the silent killer ‘disempowers anyone who displays ability and ambition under

the illusion that anyone can run a business' which, to Mangundhla, as a result of its violent aura, reduces the Indigenisation policy "to racketeering by regulation" or legalised plunder by the privileged. Even with remodelling through the Production Sharing Model for extractive industries (mining, agriculture, tourism) and the Joint Empowerment Investment Model for manufacturing and services, nothing of significance has ensued, except to manage criticism and controversy.

In short, just like the rest of the BEE programme, there is little entrepreneurship worth talking about as all the new entrepreneurs do is dip into government tenders, hardly generating much business and industry for their unemployed compatriots. As Philipp observes, the entrepreneurship turns out to be an out-of-necessity drive rather than an opportunity building measure; an alibi for failed social and economic policies, with even venal jobs like arbitrage, tenderpreneurship, middlemanship or self-dealing and resource pillaging (especially the decimation of wildlife) labelled entrepreneurship. The final equation equals rising *Homo simplex*.

Summed up, multiple vicissitudes, faults and breaks complicate the capacity to deliver accomplished researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs, even among well-established institutions and, more so, across Third World scapes. Indeed, if things were as easy as the classroom puts it and as readily applicable as politics say, then the thousands of unemployed graduates and the numerous businesses that collapse at infant stages would not be such a colossal challenge. With the advent of robotics increasing joblessness, the RIE deliverable is up against a very steep incline. Currently, disturbing levels of suboptimal cognition curtail both the practical scope and potential for commercialisation of any creations and innovations. Driven by conscious and unconscious competence/incompetence is the all empirical teaching and learning imposing colossal categories of fixed facts of dubious value, while reducing the RIE deliverable to fascination with myopia. Also, on a dim note, the decline in investment research in key sectors like rural agriculture and forestry cast murky prospects for the future. Stealthily, headquarters uses the decline as evidence to gain the upper hand, dictating and entrenching bureaucratic strictures to achieve its agendas, negatively impacting institutional strength to foster *Homo technicus*.

In one of his writings, Chulu (2014) of the Bible School Business School (BSBS) criticises Africa's naïve consciousness, succumbing to the 'Goliath' development agenda of the West as opposed to the 'Davidian' approach of small, simple, affordable, alternative technologies that 'betterise' with time – the SMEs approach. Especially, rather than cling to traditional rules, like what Japan and the other east-Asian Tigers did, Africa should change the rules and adopt much more aggressive methods of harnessing the needed technology, even if it means espionage or pirating it. Commenting on the US's accusation of China for economic espionage, the New Yorker (2014) observes how throughout the ages such espionage has been the ball game, by the USA itself, by Japan and today, by China, without exception. As he puts it "when you are not yet generating a lot of IP on your own, you imitate. The tactic of using piracy to leapfrog ahead (technologically) is an idea China stole from us (the US)." And the espionage wars have not ended.

Sadly, Africa's historically soft, genteel 'catch up' mantra, now cast as 'technology diplomacy' involving elaborate third party technology transfers, is but a recipe for prolonged slavery to technological imperialism. The continent is infamous for 'short cuts' to high stake consumerism of already ripe products with minimal sweat (for example, medical tourism). Indeed, vision statements like '...professionalism rooted in integrity' mean that reverse engineering and similar alternatives lie outside the institutional scope. The trials and tribulations of the politics notwithstanding, it was time for a paradigm shift to interfere with the so called 'rules of fair play' that close rather than open up research space against the continent and its institutions. Such wisdom remains embroiled in the power politics to see the light of day.

More than anything else, epistemologically, it appears the vision-mission statements reincarnate the dilemmas of exaggeration, utopianism and manipulative sophistry symptomatic of the cycle of disvalue education. The conventional pedagogy escalates the deculturation and acquisition of impertinent skills and values, ironically, which the curriculum promises to resolve, paradoxically, ushering numerous mischaracterizations of the education, including Pipim's gridlocked mind-sets. The disabled curriculum investments portray the derailed proficiency of Zimbabwe's higher education, clearly advancing technological tokenism. The system is overwhelmed by this problem whose narrative conjures up empty promises and/or endless blame-games.

Conclusion

Aggregated, the RIE deliverable is the springboard to the technological infinite and national self-reliance. It is what the whole collection of *esprit de corps* is all about to fulfil the vision of the Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education, Science and Technology Development to 'guarantee Zimbabwe as a leader in the creation and use of new and existing knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources.' Driven by the traditional catch up myth and seemingly pursued with paranoiac vigour, it is still to scale the rigours of technological dynamism with high-tech impact.

This is in the face of myriad enduring faults and breaks which spawn a distressed RIE deliverable, capping mediocre performances and endless disappointments. Trapped in the identity crisis to replicate the colonial method, catalytic deliberation and process formalization remain skewed so much that the vision-mission claims of 'knowledge hub', 'new knowledge generation', or 'technological solutions' are not borne out by facts. Not only is external knowledge dominating programme delivery, the 'adopt and adapt' mantra re-entrenches the dictates of technocapitalist imperialism with the RIE deliverable more exploitative than facilitative, while also remote and lying beyond the oral worldviews of the local populations. In the end the system is unable to pragmatically integrate theory with practice or to transform idealism into reality, hence, producing individuals whose schooling borders on disvalue education.

It behoves the higher education fraternity to ingeminate forceful processes and mechanisms that deepen the science to leverage a functioning learning product that is able to translate the philosophy of 'Fusion of Knowledge' into a spontaneous uptake to craft effective researches,

innovations, entrepreneurships and other socio-economic resources. While the *pracademic* curriculum would be a viable starting point, the discussion lies outside the scope of this paper.

References

- Akinola, L. (2015, December 18-23) Not everybody is an entrepreneur: Masiyiwa. Business News *Zimbabwe Independent*, Business Digest. p.6
- Bloc, E. (2014, January 24) SMEs key to economic wellbeing. *Zimbabwe Independent*. Column. p.12.
- Bindura University of Science Education (BUSE) *Annual Report 2013*. Bindura
- Bostrom, N. (2012). The Future of Human Kind. *Scientific American*. 21 March, 2012, 10:00a.m Tweet.
- Chulu B. (2014, February 14 – 20) How to bring down a business giant. The Human Capital Telescope. *Zimbabwe Independent Business Digest*. p.8
- Grasgreen, A. (2013, May 15). Career Services Must Die. Inside Higher Education. Retrieved from <https://www.insidehighered.com/news/2013/05/15/career-services-it-now-exists-must-die-new-report-argues>
- Harare Institute of Technology *Annual Report 2013*. Harare
- Harare Institute of Technology (2011) *The HIT Magazine* Vol. 1, 2011 The Innovative and Technopreneurial University. Harare
- Lee, P. (2012) Design Research: What Is It and Why Do It? IDEAS. REBOOT. Retrieved from <http://www.thereboot.org>
- Lemarchand, G. A., & Schneegans S. (2014) The Research Council of Zimbabwe: Mapping Research and Innovation in the Republic of Zimbabwe. UNESCO Go SPIN. Country Profiles in Science, Technology and Innovation Policy
- Lou, A. (2013) “There Are Only Four Jobs in the Whole World – Are You in the Right One?” 26 May 2013, 12:25pm. LinkedIn
- Lewis, H. R. (2007). *Excellence Without a Soul. Does Liberal Education have a Future?* New York: PublicAffairs
- Mabhena, C. Z. (2016a, January 31). The sweetest poison. *The Sunday News*, Opinion and Analysis. Retrieved from <http://www.sundaynews.co.zw>
- Mabhena, C. Z. (2016b, May 8 – 14). Liberating the University in Africa. *Sunday News*, Big Read Column. p.8
- Mangundhla, T. (2014. February 21–27). Indigenization an economic albatross. *Zimbabwe Independent*. Analysis. p.13
- McCarthy, T. (2012). Molecular nanotechnology and the World System. Retrieved from <http://www.mccarthy.cx/WorldSystem>
- Morley L. (2003). *Quality and Power in Higher Education*. McGraw-Hill International, UK
- New Yorker (2014, July 4 – 10) ‘US accuse China of economic espionage’ *Zimbabwe Independent*, Business Digest. p.18
- National University of Science and Technology *Vice-Chancellor’s Annual Report 2013*. Bulawayo.
- Ngwenya, B. (2016, May 4 – 8). Economic Focus: Zim economy deteriorating into a cash market economy. *Sunday News*, Finance. p.B2
- Nyathi, J. (2014, June 13). The failure of independence. *The Chronicle*. Opinion. p.5
- Philipp, J. (2010) *Explosive Youth*. In D&C, Vol.5 (37), 190–193
- Pipim, S. K. (2013). AFRICA MUST THINK. Thought nuggets from *The Transformed Mind: Changing the World by Being Changed*. Retrieved from <http://www.drpipim.org>
- Robertson, J. (2015, May 1 to 7). Industrialisation in reverse. *Zimbabwe Independent*. Opinion. p.12

- Schramm, V. "Forbes Entrepreneurs. 5 Reasons why Undergrad Entrepreneurship Courses Aren't Producing Entrepreneurs." 15 July 2013, 10:23a.m. Tweet
- Suarez-Villa, L. (n.d.). Technocapitalism and the Information Society - The World Summit in Reflection. University of California School of Social Ecology. Retrieved from <https://cyber.harvard.edu/wsis/Suarez-Villa.html>
- Suarez-Villa, L. (2014). Corporate Power, Oligopolies, and the Crisis of the State. Albany, State University of New York Press. Retrieved from <https://www.amazon.com/Corporate-Power-Oligopolies-Crisis-State-ebook/dp/B00QXFGBG8>
- The Thiel Institute (2011). Retrieved from <http://www.thiel.edu/>
- Wright, M. (2013, November 20). Entrepreneurs: nature or nurture? Cause4, The Telegraph. Retrieved from <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/finance/businessclub/10462559/Entrepreneurs-nature-or-nurture.html>